

Weak LA-hypergroups; Neutrosophy, Enumeration and Redox Reaction

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Abstract. The main motivation of this article is to introduce the theme of Neutrosophic triplet(NT) H_v -LA-Groups. This inspiration is received from the structure of weak non-associative Neutrosophic triplet(NT) structures. For it, firstly, we define that each element x have left neut(x) and left anti(x), which may or may not be unique. We further introduce the notion of neutrosophic triplet H_v -LA-subgroups and neutrosophic weak homomorphism on NT H_v -LA-Group. Secondly, presented NT H_v -LA-Group and develop two Mathematica Packages which help to check the left invertive law, weak left invertive law and reproductive axiom. Finally established a numerical example to validate the proposed approach in chemistry using redox reactions.

Keywords: H_v LA-groups, NT sets, Neutro weak homomorphism, Mathematica Packages, Chemical applications,

1. Introduction

Neutrosophic logic: Neutrosophy is the new branch of philosophy that studies the origin and scope of neutralities, as well as their interaction with different ideational spectra. Smarandache used the idea of neutrosophic set. He defined the theme of t -membership, i -membership and f -membership, so neutrosophic logic generalize all previous versions, see [1], [2], [3]. Many researchers have studied neutrosophic cubic set, complex neutrosophic cubic set, N-cubic set and their applications in real life problems, see [52–55]. Further Abdel-Basset et. al., use neutrosophic set in different direction and discuss their use in real life problems [56–60] More

about the neutrosophic algebraic structures we refer the reader [4–6] and [7–12]. For the NT groups see [13–18].

Hyperstructures theory: In 1934, Marty [19] introduced the theme of hyperstructures. More about the hyperstructures we refer the reader [20–22]. The idea of weak structure, which is known as H_v -structure is introduced by Vougiouklis [23], see also [24–31]. In 2007 Davvaz and Fotea mainly dedicated to the study of hyperring theory [32]. Davvaz and Vougiouklis [33], published recently a new book having title "A walk through weak hyperstructures, H_v -Structures" with some interesting applications of hyperstructures.

Left Invertive Structures: Kazim and Naseerudin [34] laid the idea of left almost semigroup (denoted by LA-semigroup). Afterwards, Mushtaq [35] and some other researcher, further worked in detail on the structure of LA-semigroup, see papers [36–42]. Hila and Dine [43] in 2011, furnished the idea of LA-semihypergroup. More detail can be seen in [44], [45], [46], [47], [48], [49], [50], [51].

Our Approach: This paper is the continuation of our published paper [18] and it consists of 6 sections. We arrange this work as: In section 2, we collected some of the relevant material after the introduction. In section 3, we give a new class of algebraic hyperstructure known as NT H_v -LA-Group, which is the main theme of LA-Group, LA-hypergroup, H_v -LA-Group. In NT H_v -LA-Group each element k have left neut(k) and left anti(k), which may or may not unique. We also define the neutro weak homomorphism on NT H_v -LA-Group. Moreover, we discuss many interesting properties of NT H_v -LA-Groups. In section 4, we provide the construction of NT H_v -LA-Groups with the two Mathematica Packages which help to check the left invertive law, weak left invertive law and reproductive axiom. In section 5, we present the application of propose structure in chemical reactions. In section 6, we end with the concluding remarks.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we added some basic definition and result, which helped to prove the result of our proposed structure.

Definition 2.1. [44] "A hypergroupoid (\aleph, \circ) is called LA-semihypergroup, if it satisfies the following law

$$(b_1 \circ b_2) \circ b_3 = (b_3 \circ b_2) \circ b_1 \text{ for all } b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \aleph.$$

”

Example 2.2. [44] "Let $\aleph = Z$ if we define $b_1 \circ b_2 = b_2 - b_1 + 3Z$, where $b_1, b_2 \in Z$. Then (\aleph, \circ) become LA-semihypergroup."

Definition 2.3. [24] "The hyperoperation $*$: $\mathfrak{N} \times \mathfrak{N} \longrightarrow P^*(\mathfrak{N})$ is called weakly associative hyperoperation (abbreviated as WASS) if for any $b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \mathfrak{N}$

$$(b_1 * b_2) * b_3 \cap b_1 * (b_2 * b_3) \neq \phi$$

"

Definition 2.4. [24] "The hyperoperation is weakly commutative (abbreviated as COW) if for any $b_1, b_2 \in \mathfrak{N}$

$$b_1 * b_2 \cap b_2 * b_1 \neq \phi$$

"

Definition 2.5. [47] "Let \mathfrak{N} be non-empty set and $*$ be hyperoperation on \mathfrak{N} . Then $(\mathfrak{N}, *)$ is called an \mathfrak{N}_v -LA-semigroup, if it satisfies the weak left invertive law for all $b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \mathfrak{N}$

$$(b_1 * b_2) * b_3 \cap (b_3 * b_2) * b_1 \neq \phi$$

"

Example 2.6. [47] "Let $\mathfrak{N} = (0, \infty)$ we define $b_1 * b_2 = \left\{ \frac{b_2}{b_1+1}, \frac{b_2}{b_1} \right\}$ where $b_1, b_2 \in \mathfrak{N}$. Then for all $b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \mathfrak{N}$. Then for all $b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \mathfrak{N}$ satisfies $(b_1 * b_2) * b_3 \cap (b_3 * b_2) * b_1 \neq \phi$. Hence $(\mathfrak{N}, *)$ is an H_v -LA-semigroup."

3. Neutrosophic Triplet(NT) H_v -LA-Groups

In this section, we define a new class of hyper algebraic structure known as NT H_v -LA-group and discuss some results on NT H_v -LA-group.

Definition 3.1. Let $(\mathfrak{N}, *)$ be a left (resp., right, pure left, pure right) NT set. Then \mathfrak{N} is called left (resp., right, pure left, pure right) NT H_v -LA-group, if it satisfies the following axioms,

- (1) $(\mathfrak{N}, *)$ is well defined,
- (2) $(\mathfrak{N}, *)$ satisfies the weak left invertive law, i.e, $(b_1 * b_2) * b_3 \cap (b_3 * b_2) * b_1 \neq \phi$ for all $b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \mathfrak{N}$,
- (3) $\mathfrak{N} * b_1 = \mathfrak{N} = \mathfrak{N} * b_1$ for all $b_1 \in \mathfrak{N}$.

Example 3.2. Let $\mathfrak{N} = \{b_1, b_2, b_3\}$ be a finite set. The hyperoperation $*$ is defined in Table-1

*	b_1	b_2	b_3
b_1	b_1	$\{b_1, b_2\}$	$\{b_1, b_3\}$
b_2	b_3	$\{\mathfrak{N}\}$	$\{b_1, b_2\}$
b_3	b_2	$\{b_1, b_3\}$	$\{\mathfrak{N}\}$

Table-1, neutrosophic triplet H_v -LA-group

Here all elements of \aleph satisfy the weak left invertive law. Also left invertive law is not hold in \aleph , i.e.

$$\aleph = (b_1 * b_2) * b_3 \neq (b_3 * b_2) * b_1 = \{b_1, b_2\}.$$

Alike, associative law is not hold in \aleph i.e.

$$\aleph = (b_3 * b_3) * b_1 \neq b_3 * (b_3 * b_1) = \{b_1, b_3\}.$$

Even, weak associative law is not valid here

$$\{b_2\} = (b_2 * b_1) * b_1 \cap b_2 * (b_1 * b_1) = \{b_3\} = \phi.$$

Here $(b_1, b_1, b_1), (b_2, b_1, b_2), (b_3, b_1, b_3)$ are left NT sets. Hence $(\aleph, *)$ is a NT H_v -LA-group.

Proposition 3.3. *Let $(\aleph, *)$ be a pure right NT H_v -LA-group. Then $neut(b_1) * b_2 = neut(b_1) * b_3$ if $anti(b_1) * b_2 = anti(b_1) * b_3$ for all $b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \aleph$.*

Proof. Suppose $(\aleph, *)$ is a pure right NT H_v -LA-group and $anti(b_1) * b_2 = anti(b_1) * b_3$ for $b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \aleph$. Multiply b_1 to the left side of $(b_1 * anti(b_1)) * b_2 = (b_1 * anti(b_1)) * b_3$,

$$\begin{aligned} (b_1 * anti(b_1)) * b_2 &= (b_1 * anti(b_1)) * b_3 \\ neut(b_1) * b_2 &= neut(b_1) * b_3 \text{ (because } neut(b_1) = b_1 * anti(b_1) \text{)}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $neut(b_1) * b_2 = neut(b_1) * b_3$. \square

Theorem 3.4. *Let $(\aleph, *)$ be a pure right NT H_v -LA-group. Then $neut(b_1) * neut(b_1) = neut(b_1)$.*

Proof. Consider $neut(b_1) * neut(b_1) = neut(b_1)$. Multiply first with b_1 to the right, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} (b_1 * (neut(b_1))) * neut(b_1) &= b_1 * neut(b_1) \\ ((b_1 * neut(b_1)) * neut(b_1)) &= b_1 \\ b_1 * neut(b_1) &= b_1 \\ b_1 &= b_1. \end{aligned}$$

This shows that $neut(b_1) * neut(b_1) = neut(b_1)$. \square

Theorem 3.5. *Let $(\aleph, *)$ be a pure right NT H_v -LA-group. Then $neut(b_1) * anti(b_1) = anti(b_1)$.*

Proof. Let $(\mathfrak{N}, *)$ be a pure right NT H_v -LA-group. Multiply b_1 to the left of both side $neut(b_1) * anti(b_1) = anti(b_1)$, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} (b_1 * (neut(b_1))) * anti(b_1) &= b_1 * anti(b_1) \\ b_1 * anti(b_1) &= neut(b_1) \\ neut(b_1) &= neut(b_1) \\ neut(b_1) &= neut(b_1) \end{aligned}$$

This shows that $neut(b_1) * anti(b_1) = anti(b_1)$. \square

Theorem 3.6. *Let $(\mathfrak{N}, *)$ be a pure left NT H_v -LA-group. Then $neut(anti(b_1)) = neut(b_1)$.*

Proof. Let $neut(anti(b_1)) = neut(b_1)$. If we put $anti(b_1) = b_2$, then

$$\begin{aligned} neut(b_2) &= neut(b_1). \text{ Post multiply by } b_2 \\ neut(b_2) * b_2 &= neut(b_1) * b_2 \\ b_2 &= neut(b_1) * b_2 \\ anti(b_1) &= neut(b_1) * anti(b_1), \text{ as } b_2 = anti(b_1) \\ anti(b_1) &= anti(b_1), \text{ By Theorem 3.5 } neut(b_1) * anti(b_1) = anti(b_1). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $neut(anti(b_1)) = neut(b_1)$. \square

Definition 3.7. A non-empty subset B of a left NT H_v -LA-group $(\mathfrak{N}, *)$ is called a left NT H_v -LA-subgroup of \mathfrak{N} , if B itself form NT H_v -LA-group under same hyperoperation defined in \mathfrak{N} .

Example 3.8. Let $\mathfrak{N} = \{b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4\}$ and the hyperoperation is defined in the Table-2

*	b_1	b_2	b_3	b_4
b_1	b_1	b_2	b_3	b_4
b_2	b_3	$\{b_1, b_3\}$	$\{b_2, b_3\}$	b_4
b_3	b_2	$\{b_1, b_3\}$	$\{b_1, b_3\}$	b_4
b_4	b_4	b_4	b_4	$\{b_1, b_2, b_3\}$

Table-2, neutrosophic triplet H_v -LA-group

Here (b_1, b_1, b_1) , (b_2, b_1, b_2) , (b_3, b_2, b_2) and (b_4, b_3, b_4) are NT sets. As all elements of \mathfrak{N} satisfy the weak left invertive law but \mathfrak{N} do not satisfies the left invertive law, associative law and

weak associative law i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \{b_1, b_3\} &= (b_2 * b_2) * b_3 \neq (b_3 * b_2) * b_2 = \{b_1, b_2, b_3\} \\ \text{and } \{b_1, b_3\} &= (b_2 * b_2) * b_3 \neq b_2 * (b_2 * b_3) = \{b_1, b_2, b_3\}. \\ \text{Also } \{b_2\} &= (b_2 * b_1) * b_1 \cap b_2 * (b_1 * b_1) = \{b_3\} = \phi. \end{aligned}$$

So $(\mathfrak{N}, *)$ is a NT H_v -LA-group. Here $\mathfrak{b} = \{b_1, b_2, b_3\}$ is a NT H_v -LA-subgroup of \mathfrak{N} .

Lemma 3.9. *If $(\mathfrak{N}, *)$ is a NT H_v -LA group, then*

$$\begin{aligned} (b_1 * b_2) * (b_3 * b_4) \cap (b_1 * b_3) * (b_2 * b_4) &\neq \phi, \\ \text{hold for all } b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4 &\in \mathfrak{N}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} &(b_1 * b_2) * (b_3 * b_4) \\ &= (b_1 * b_2) * g, \text{ where } g = (b_3 * b_4) \\ &= (b_1 * b_2) * g \cap (g * b_2) * b_1 \text{ by the weak left invertive law} \\ &= (b_1 * b_2) * g \cap (g * b_2) * b_1 \text{ by the weak-left invertive law} \\ &= (b_1 * b_2) * g \cap \{(g * b_2) * b_1\} \text{ by the weak-left invertive law} \\ &= (b_1 * b_2) * (b_3 * b_4) \cap \{(b_3 * b_4) * b_2\} * b_1, \text{ where } g = (b_3 * b_4) \\ &= (b_1 * b_2) * (b_3 * b_4) \cap \{(b_3 * b_4) * b_2\} \cap (b_2 * b_4) * b_3 * b_1 \\ &= (b_1 * b_2) * (b_3 * b_4) \cap \{(b_3 * b_4) * b_2\} * b_1 \cap \{(b_2 * b_4) * b_3\} * b_1 \\ &= (b_1 * b_2) * (b_3 * b_4) \cap \left\{ \begin{array}{l} ((b_3 * b_4) * b_2) * b_1 \cap (b_1 * b_2) * (b_3 * b_4) \\ \cap \{(b_2 * b_4) * b_3\} * b_1 \cap (b_1 * b_3) * (b_2 * b_4) \end{array} \right\} \rightarrow (1) \end{aligned}$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (b_1 * b_3) * (b_2 * b_4) \\
 &= (b_1 * b_3) * g, \text{ where } g = (b_2 * b_4) \\
 &= (b_1 * b_3) * g \cap (g * b_3) * b_1 \text{ by the weak left invertive law} \\
 &= (b_1 * b_3) * g \cap (g * b_3) * b_1 \text{ by the weak-left invertive law} \\
 &= (b_1 * b_3) * g \cap \{(g * b_3) * b_1\} \text{ by the weak-left invertive law} \\
 &= (b_1 * b_3) * (b_2 * b_4) \cap \{(b_2 * b_4) * b_3\} * b_1, \text{ where } g = (b_2 * b_4) \\
 &= (b_1 * b_3) * (b_2 * b_4) \cap \{((b_2 * b_4) * b_3) \cap (b_3 * b_4) * b_2\} * b_1 \\
 &= (b_1 * b_3) * (b_2 * b_4) \cap \{((b_2 * b_4) * b_3) * b_1\} \cap \{((b_3 * b_4) * b_2) * b_1\} \\
 &= (b_1 * b_3) * (b_2 * b_4) \cap \left\{ \begin{array}{l} ((b_2 * b_4) * b_3) * b_1 \cap (b_1 * b_3) * (b_2 * b_4) \\ \cap \{((b_3 * b_4) * b_2) * b_1 \cap (b_1 * b_2) * (b_3 * b_4)\} \end{array} \right\} \rightarrow (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

From (1) and (2) we have $(b_1 * b_2) * (b_3 * b_4) \cap (b_1 * b_3) * (b_2 * b_4) \neq \phi$, hold for all $b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4 \in \mathfrak{N}$. This law is known as weak medial law. \square

Proposition 3.10. *Let (\mathfrak{N}, \circ) be a NT H_v -LA-group with left identity e and $\phi \neq A \subseteq \mathfrak{N}$. If $(A \circ (A \circ b_1)) \circ b_2 \cap (A \circ (A \circ b_2)) \circ b_1 \neq \phi \forall b_1, b_2 \in \mathfrak{N}$ and we define a hyperoperation A_R^\otimes on \mathfrak{N} as $b_1 A_R^\otimes b_2 = (b_1 \circ b_2) \circ A$, then $(\mathfrak{N}, A_R^\otimes)$ become a NT H_v -LA-group.*

Proof. Let $b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \mathfrak{N}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 (b_1 A_R^\otimes b_2) A_R^\otimes b_3 &= ((b_1 \circ b_2) \circ A) A_R^\otimes b_3 \\
 &= (((b_1 \circ b_2) \circ A) \circ b_3) \circ A \\
 &= ((b_3 \circ A) \circ (b_1 \circ b_2)) \circ A \\
 &= (A \circ (A \circ b_3)) \circ (b_2 \circ b_1) \\
 &= b_2 \circ ((A \circ (A \circ b_3)) \circ b_1)
 \end{aligned}$$

and on the other hand

$$\begin{aligned}
 (b_3 A_R^\otimes b_2) A_R^\otimes b_1 &= ((b_3 \circ b_2) \circ A) A_R^\otimes b_1 \\
 &= (((b_3 \circ b_2) \circ A) \circ b_3) \circ A \\
 &= ((b_1 \circ A) \circ (b_3 \circ b_2)) \circ A \\
 &= (A \circ (A \circ b_1)) \circ (b_2 \circ b_3) \\
 &= b_2 \circ ((A \circ (A \circ b_1)) \circ b_3)
 \end{aligned}$$

but

$$b_2 \circ ((A \circ (A \circ b_3)) \circ b_1) \cap b_2 \circ ((A \circ (A \circ b_1)) \circ b_3) \neq \phi$$

for all $b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \aleph$. It follows that

$$(b_1 A_R^{\otimes} b_2) A_R^{\otimes} b_3 \cap (b_3 A_R^{\otimes} b_2) A_R^{\otimes} b_1 \neq \phi.$$

Next, we have

$$b_1 A_R^{\otimes} \aleph = (b_1 \circ \aleph) \circ A = \aleph \text{ also } H A_R^{\otimes} b_1 = (\aleph \circ b_1) \circ A = \aleph.$$

Hence (\aleph, A_R^{\otimes}) become an H_v -LA-group. \square

Definition 3.11. Let (\aleph_1, \circ) and $(\aleph_2, *)$ be two NT H_v -LA-groups. The map $f : \aleph_1 \rightarrow \aleph_2$ is called neutro homomorphism, if for all $b_1, b_2 \in \aleph_1$, the following conditions hold,

1. $f(b_1 \circ b_2) \cap f(b_1) * f(b_2) \neq \phi$,
2. $f(\text{neut}(b_1)) \cap \text{neut}(f(b_1)) \neq \phi$,
3. $f(\text{anti}(b_1)) \cap \text{anti}(f(b_1)) \neq \phi$.

Example 3.12. Let $\aleph_1 = \{v_1, v_2, v_3\}$ and $\aleph_2 = \{b_1, b_2, b_3\}$ are two finite sets, where $(\aleph_1, *)$ and (\aleph_2, \circ) are NT H_v -LA-groups, the hyperoperation is defined in following tables 3,4:

*	v_1	v_2	v_3
v_1	$\{v_1\}$	$\{v_2\}$	$\{v_3\}$
v_2	$\{v_3\}$	$\{v_1, v_2\}$	$\{v_2\}$
v_3	$\{v_2\}$	$\{v_3\}$	$\{v_3, v_1\}$

Table-3, neutrosophic triplet H_v -LA-group

and

\circ	b_1	b_2	b_3
b_1	b_1	$\{b_1, b_2\}$	$\{b_1, b_3\}$
b_2	b_3	$\{\aleph\}$	$\{b_1, b_2\}$
b_3	b_2	$\{b_1, b_3\}$	$\{\aleph\}$

Table-4, neutrosophic triplet H_v -LA-group

The mapping $f : \aleph_1 \rightarrow \aleph_2$ is defined by $f(v_1) = b_1$, $f(v_2) = b_2$, $f(v_3) = b_3$. Then clearly f is a neutro homomorphism.

4. Construction Of Neutrosophic triplet(NT) H_v -LA-groups

In this section we provide the construction of NT H_v -LA-groups and develop two Mathematica Packages which help us to check the left invertive law, weak left invertive law and reproductive axiom.

Consider a finite set \aleph , such that $|\aleph| > 2$. Define the hyperoperation \circ on \aleph as follows

$$b_i \circ b_j = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} b_j & \text{for } i = 1 \\ b_b \text{ for } j = 1 \text{ and } b \equiv 2 - i \pmod{|\aleph|} & \\ \aleph & \text{for } i = j, i \neq 1, j \neq 1 \\ b_i & \text{otherwise, for } i \prec j \text{ or } i \succ j \end{array} \right\}$$

and if *neut* (b_i) and *anti* (b_i) exist in \aleph . Then \aleph under the hyperoperation \circ forms a NT H_v -LA-group.

The above construction can be explained with the help of an example.

Example 4.1. Let $\aleph = \{b_1, b_2, b_3\}$ under the binary hyperoperation \circ defined in Table-5

\circ	b_1	b_2	b_3
b_1	b_1	b_2	b_3
b_2	b_3	\aleph	b_2
b_3	b_2	b_3	\aleph

Table-5, neutrosophic triplet H_v -LA-group

Here (b_1, b_1, b_1) , (b_2, b_1, b_2) and (b_3, b_1, b_3) are NT set. One can see that \circ satisfy the weak left invertive law, also \circ is non-left invertive and non-associative i.e.

$$\aleph = (b_3 \circ b_3) \circ b_2 \neq (b_2 \circ b_3) \circ b_3 = b_2$$

$$\text{and } \aleph = (b_2 \circ b_2) \circ b_1 \neq b_2 \circ (b_2 \circ b_1) = b_2.$$

Also it is not $WASS(b_2 \circ b_1) \circ b_1 \cap b_2 \circ (b_1 \circ b_1) = \phi$. Hence (\aleph, \circ) is a NT H_v -LA-group. The result of table can easily be generalized to n elements.

Remark 4.2. In NT H_v -LA-group, the property of H_v -LA-group can be checked by using the mathematica packages. The mathematica package(A) used to check the left invertive property and mathematica package(B) is used to check the weak non associative hypergroups. We paste the mathematica packages as under:

```

BeginPackage["LeftAlmostHyperGroupTest"];
Clear["LeftAlmostHyperGroupTest'*"];
Begin["'Private'"]; Clear["LeftAlmostHyperGroupTest'Private'*"];
LeftAlmostHyperGroupTest[LookupTable_List] :=
  Table[If[ReproductivityTest[LookupTable[[j]],
    If[LeftInvertiveTest[LookupTable[[j]], True, False],
    False], {j, 1, Length[LookupTable]}];
LeftInvertiveTest[LookupTable1_List] := Module[{i, j, k, len, test}, i = 1;
  j = 1;
  k = 1;
  test = True;
  len = Length[LookupTable1];
  While[test && i ≤ len, test = Union[Flatten[Union[Extract[LookupTable1,
    Distribute[{LookupTable1[[i, j]], {k}], List]]]] = Union[Flatten[Union[
    Extract[LookupTable1, Distribute[{LookupTable1[[k, j]], {i}], List]]]]];
  k = k + 1; If[k > len, k = 1; j = j + 1;
  If[j > len, i = i + 1; j = 1];];];
  Return[test];
ReproductivityTest[LookupTable1_List] :=
  Union[Apply[Union, LookupTable1, 1] == {Range[1, Length[LookupTable1]]} &&
  Union[Apply[Union, Transpose[LookupTable1], 1] == {Range[1, Length[LookupTable1]}];
End[];
EndPackage[];

```

Mathematica Package (A)

and

```

BeginPackage["WeakLeftAlmostHyperGroupTest"];
Clear["WeakLeftAlmostHyperGroupTest'*"];
Begin["'Private'"]; Clear["WeakLeftAlmostHyperGroupTest'Private'*"];
WeakLeftAlmostHyperGroupTest[LookupTable_List] :=
  Table[If[ReproductivityTest[LookupTable[[j]]],
    If[WeakLeftInvertiveTest[LookupTable[[j]]], True, False],
    False], {j, 1, Length[LookupTable]};
WeakLeftInvertiveTest[LookupTable1_List] := Module[{i, j, k, len, test,  $\emptyset$ }, i = 1;
  j = 1; k = 1;
  test = True;
  len = Length[LookupTable1];
   $\emptyset$  = NullSet;
  While[test && i  $\leq$  len,
    test = Union[Flatten[Union[Extract[LookupTable1, Distribute[{LookupTable1[[i, j]],
      {k}], List]]]]  $\cap$  Union[Flatten[Union[Extract[LookupTable1,
      Distribute[{LookupTable1[[k, j]], {i}], List]]]]]  $\neq$  {};
    k = k + 1; If[k > len, k = 1; j = j + 1;
    If[j > len, i = i + 1; j = 1];];];
  Return[test];
ReproductivityTest[LookupTable1_List] :=
  Union[Apply[Union, LookupTable1, 1]] == {Range[1, Length[LookupTable1]]} &&
  Union[Apply[Union, Transpose[LookupTable1], 1]] == {Range[1, Length[LookupTable1]]};
End[];
EndPackage[];

WeakLeftAlmostHyperGroupTest.m;

```

Mathematica Package (B)

5. Application of Our proposed Structure

In the universe, the femininity, masculinity and neutrality exist. If we take the small particle, the small particle is an atom. The atom consists of three particle electrons, proton and neutron. So, from the above idea of the universe gave the concept of NT set. (Masculine, Neutral, feminine) and (Proton, Neutron, Electron) are the example of NT set.

There are three workers working in a factory. All three workers are disabled. The first worker has the right hand and no left hand. Factory made such a machine on which he can work with his right hand. The second worker has left hand but no right hand. Such a machine is made for him, on which he worked with his left hand. The third worker has an issue working with both of his hand. Such a machine is made for him, he works with his legs. All of these

three worker’s working performance is shown by the following Table-6.

\otimes	L	R	N
L	R	N	$\{L, N\}$
R	N	L	$\{R, N\}$
N	L	R	N

Table-6, neutrosophic triplet H_v -LA-group

In this table L represents the performance the worker, who work with his left hand. R represents the performance of the worker, who work with his right hand and N represents the performance of the worker, whose both hand are not functioning properly. Let $F = \{L, R, N\}$ be a finite set the hyperoperation is defined in the above table, and $(L, N, R), (R, N, L)$ and (N, L, L) are left NT set. (F, \otimes) is a NT H_v -LA group.

5.1. *Chemical example of Neutrosophic Triplet(NT) H_v -LA- group*

The best example of NT H_v -LA-group in chemical reaction is a redox reaction.

Redox reaction: The chemical reaction in which one specie loss the electron and other specie gain the electron. Oxidation mean loss of electron. Reduction mean gain of electron. The redox reaction is a vital for biochemical reaction and industrial process. The electron transfer in cell and oxidation of glucose in the human body are the example of redox reaction. The reaction between hydrogen and fluorine is an example of redox reaction i.e.

Each half reaction has standard reduction potential (E^0) which is equal to the potential difference at equilibrium under the standard condition of an electrochemical cell in which the cathode reaction is half reaction considered and anode is a standard hydrogen electrode (SHE). For the redox reaction, the potential of cell is defined as

$$E^\circ_{cell} = E^\circ_{cathode} - E^\circ_{anode}$$

where E°_{anode} is the standard potential at the anode and $E^\circ_{cathode}$ is the standard potential at the cathode as given in the table of standard electrode potential. Now consider the redox reaction of Mn

Manganese having a variable oxidation state of 0,+1,+2,+3,+4,+5,+6,+7. If we take $Mn^0, Mn^{+4}, Mn^{+3}, Mn^{+2}$ together we will get pure redox reaction. The flow chart is given as

Flow chart

Mn species with different oxidation state react with themselves. All possible reactions are presented in the following Table-7

\oplus	Mn^0	Mn^{+1}	Mn^{+2}	Mn^{+3}	Mn^{+4}
Mn^0	Mn^0	$\{Mn^0, Mn^{+1}\}$	$\{Mn^0, Mn^{+2}\}$	$\{Mn^0, Mn^{+3}\}$	$\{Mn^0, Mn^{+4}\}$
Mn^{+1}	$\{Mn^0, Mn^{+1}\}$	$\{Mn^0, Mn^{+2}\}$	$\{Mn^0, Mn^{+3}\}$	$\{Mn^{+2}\}$	$\{Mn^{+1}, Mn^{+4}\}$
Mn^{+2}	Mn^{+1}	$\{Mn^0, Mn^{+3}\}$	$\{Mn^{+1}, Mn^{+3}\}$	$\{Mn^{+1}, Mn^{+4}\}$	$\{Mn^{+2}, Mn^{+4}\}$
Mn^{+3}	$\{Mn^0, Mn^{+3}\}$	$\{Mn^{+1}, Mn^{+3}\}$	$\{Mn^{+2}, Mn^{+3}\}$	Mn^{+3}	$\{Mn^{+3}, Mn^{+4}\}$
Mn^{+4}	$\{Mn^0, Mn^{+4}\}$	$\{Mn^{+1}, Mn^{+4}\}$	$\{Mn^{+2}, Mn^{+4}\}$	$\{Mn^{+3}, Mn^{+4}\}$	Mn^{+4}

Table-7, All possible reactions

The standard reduction potentials (E^0) for conversion of each oxidation state to another are

$$E^0 (Mn^{+4}/Mn^{+3}) = +0.95,$$

$$E^0 (Mn^{+3}/Mn^{+2}) = +1.542,$$

$$E^0 (Mn^{+2}/Mn^{+1}) = -0.59,$$

$$E^0 (Mn^{+1}/Mn^{+0}) = 0.296.$$

If we replace

$$Mn^0 = b_1, Mn^{+1} = b_2, Mn^{+2} = b_3, Mn^{+3} = b_4, Mn^{+4} = b_5,$$

then we obtain the following Table-8

\oplus	b_1	b_2	b_3	b_4	b_5
b_1	$\{b_1\}$	$\{b_1, b_2\}$	$\{b_1, b_3\}$	$\{b_1, b_4\}$	$\{b_1, b_5\}$
b_2	$\{b_1, b_2\}$	$\{b_1, b_3\}$	$\{b_1, b_4\}$	$\{b_3\}$	$\{b_2, b_5\}$
b_3	$\{b_1, b_3\}$	$\{b_1, b_4\}$	$\{b_2, b_4\}$	$\{b_2, b_5\}$	$\{b_3, b_5\}$
b_4	$\{b_1, b_4\}$	$\{b_2, b_4\}$	$\{b_3, b_4\}$	$\{b_4\}$	$\{b_4, b_5\}$
b_5	$\{b_1, b_5\}$	$\{b_2, b_5\}$	$\{b_3, b_5\}$	$\{b_4, b_5\}$	$\{b_5\}$

Table-8, NT H_v -LA-group

As all elements of \aleph satisfy the weak left invertive law but \aleph do not satisfy the left invertive law, associative law and weak associative law

$$\begin{aligned} \{b_1, b_3\} &= (b_2 \oplus b_2) \oplus b_1 \neq (b_1 \oplus b_2) \oplus b_2 = \{b_1, b_2, b_3\}, \\ \{b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4\} &= (b_2 \oplus b_2) \oplus b_3 \neq b_2 \oplus (b_2 \oplus b_3) = \{b_1, b_2, b_3\}, \\ \text{and } (b_2 \oplus b_4) \oplus b_4 &= \{b_2, b_5\} \cap b_3 = b_2 \oplus (b_4 \oplus b_4) = \phi \end{aligned}$$

Here $(b_1, b_1, b_1), (b_2, b_4, b_3), (b_3, b_4, b_2), (b_4, b_5, b_3)$ and (b_5, b_4, b_4) are NT sets. Hence (\aleph, \oplus) is a NT H_v -LA-group.

Remark 5.1. NT set, which helps the chemist to take the state of M_n which react or not react easily with other state or themselves. M_n^{+0} plays the role of neutra with different oxidation state and themselves. If the M_n have the same neutra and anti, it means that Mn having equal chances of loss or gain of electron.

6. Difference between the proposed work and existing methods

Our proposed structure has two main purpose,

- 1) This structure generalize the structure of groups, LA-groups, semigroups, LA-semigroup and as well as the hyper versions of above mentioned structures.
- 2) As NT set has the ability to capture indeterminacy in a much better way so our proposed structure of NT LA-semigroups can handle the uncertainty in a better way as we have seen in the Redox reaction.

7. Conclusions

In this article, we have studied and introduced NT H_v LA- groups. We presented some result on NT H_v LA-groups and construction of NT H_v -LA groups. We defined the neutro homomorphism on NT H_v LA groups. Also, we use the Mathematica packages to check the properties of left invertive and weak left invertive. Our defined structure have an interesting application in chemistry redox reaction.

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